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PROJECT REPORT - AERODYNAMICS OF TRANSPORT VEHICLES

Numerical and experimental study on headwind and side-wind effects on a freight train model

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Introduction

The purpose of this study is to investigate the interaction between the cross-wind and a model of a freight train considering two types of wagons with different shapes, taking advantage of both wind tunnel measurements and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations. A 3D printed model of a Class 66 locomotive was realized in order to estimate the aerodynamic loads at varying side-wind and Reynolds number conditions, allowing to determine force coefficients and to validate numerical results. After that, simulations for various wind angles have been carried out. A peculiar attention have been payed in the determination of the drag coefficient behaviour, given its significant impact on train power losses and the reliability of results among the two methodologies adopted.

1. Model description

The freight train object of the study is composed by a British Railway Class 66 locomotive and two different sets of FEA-B 60 ft container wagons, having the same length but characterized by a different cross sectional shape. Besides the

fact that this is a configuration widely diffused in Great Britain and Continental Europe, this structure was chosen for the availability of detailed drawings (that made it possible to generate the CAD model with *SOLIDWORKS*[®] software) and a remarkable amount of aerodynamic studies in literature (as an example, consider [1], [2] and [3]). Figure 1 shows the $1/35$ scale CAD model adopted for both wind tunnel measurements and numerical simulations. Relevant dimensions are reported within Figure 2.

Figure 1: CAD model of a British Railway Class 66 locomotive involved in wind tunnel measurements and CFD model validation.

Figure 2: Full scale train (as described by Soper [1]) and $1/35$ train model dimensions.

2. Model validation

The analysis of measurements results aimed mainly to check the plausibility of simulation outcomes, rather than inspecting the effect of the different wind angles on the train body aerodynamics. In addition to the unavoidable error due to the simple measurement setup, in fact, the biggest issue would be the uncertainty associated with the angle between the wind direction and the longitudinal axis of the train, given that the flow generated is quite turbulent and unsteady. Moreover, being the plate holes wider than threaded rod diameter (Figure 7 b) it is difficult to ensure absolute uniformity and consistency of the angle between the longitudinal axis of the train and, respectively, the wind direction and the scale reference system, making it unnecessary to perform measurements for a series of sparsely spaced angles.

2.1. CFD model

The computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis was conducted employing the open-source platform OPENFOAM for both mesh generation and simulation tasks. The flow regime was characterized by incompressible behavior, steady-state conditions, and turbulence. Specifically, the SimpleFoam solver was selected from the array of available solvers, leveraging the SIMPLE algorithm to address continuity and momentum equations. Notably, the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations were utilized, incorporating the k-

SST turbulence model for enhanced accuracy and turbulence modeling.

To validate the model, a domain that replicates the real dimensions of wind tunnel ($0.5\text{ m} \times 0.5\text{ m} \times 1\text{ m}$) was considered and simulations both for 0° and 15° cases were carried out. Different boundary conditions are assigned to the wall sections. Explicitly, a **No slip** condition was selected for wind tunnel walls, while for the other walls a **Slip** condition is considered. This setup was chosen to achieve results consistent with wind tunnel tests outcomes. Figure 5 shows as the configuration designed for 15° case allows the cell walls near the model to be parallel to the longitudinal axis of the train, while wind tunnel inlet and outlet walls are rotated.

As a starting point, an equal cell size was set and the following different configurations of mesh refinement close to the train body were considered:

1. **box 1**: refinement box with half the length of the train at the rear (for both cases)
2. **box 2**: same of 1. with one and a half times the length of the train (for both cases).
3. **dist 1**: refinement with a low distance from the surface (0.035 m for 0° , 0.04 m for 15°);
4. **dist 2**: same of 3. with a higher distance (0.05 m for 0° , 0.06 m for 15°);

Outcomes from this analysis, shown in Figure 3, highlighted similar results. Therefore, it was decided to opt for the first option (**box 1**: - Figure 4 - 5) as it allows to enclose the main part of the wake evolution in a sufficiently refined box with a lower number of cells compared to the last one.

Once defined the mesh refinement strategy, a mesh independence analysis was performed to find the lowest number of cells that could provide a correct result, allowing the computational effort of the simulation to be reduced. Keeping constant the width of the simulation domain, cell dimensions have been modified in a range of $[-30\%; +80\%]$ of the reference cell length (the one of the mesh of Figure 3). Results shown in Figure 6 highlight a stronger mesh-dependence and a worse convergence of C_l values rather than C_x ones, although the percentage deviations (except for coarser meshes) are not dramatically wide. This fact, together with the non monotonic trend of the results, is attributable to the bluff body nature of the train. Finally, this analysis led to the choice of adopting a mesh characterizes by a $+10\%$ cell length for the full train case, allowing to reduce computational effort with a reasonable accuracy of the results.

2.2. Wind tunnel setup

Measurements were collected in the open-circuit wind tunnel at the Measurement Lab of Politecnico di Milano shown in Figure 7a, characterized by a cross section of $0.5\text{ m} \times 0.5\text{ m}$ and a length of 1 m . Tunnel cross sectional area and model dimensions are consistent with the blockage ratio limits reported in the standard BS EN 14067-6:2018 [4] - Section 5.3.4.7. The air flow (which enters the tunnel after being straightened through a nozzle) is generated by a fan placed downstream, whose power can be adjusted thanks to an inverter. In order to measure the dynamic pressure of the flow, a Pitot tube connected to a pressure transducer is mounted on the top of the wind tunnel, sufficiently far from the wall and the model body to ensure a reliable free-stream flow characterization. Finally, a six-component force balance is located beneath the tunnel bottom

Figure 3: Comparison among the different refinement strategies adopted.

Figure 4: Mesh for **box 1** refinement setup, 0° case.

Figure 5: Mesh for *box 1* refinement setup, 15° case.

wall to measure aerodynamic loads. The train is connected to the scale plate through a pair of threaded rods so that the wheels were raised above the ground, in order to avoid the presence of other reaction forces.

Acquisitions with different measurement setups were performed so to have reliable data, trying to reduce systematic errors due to a poor configuration of the system. In particular, the following configurations were adopted:

- 1: this is an initial setup, aimed at checking that the system is working properly. Therefore, only a few measurements were taken. Figure 7b shows the connection between the threaded rods and the train, the window is then sealed with a thick aluminum adhesive tape.
- 2: In this setup, a great attention was payed in filtering the vibrations traveling from the train body to the balance plate. To do so, small stripes of window sealing tape were placed on tunnel ground plate and on train connection surfaces, as shown in Figure 7c-d respectively.
- 3: To check if the previous setup would give any benefit in results, all vibration insulating tapes were removed. Moreover, the scale plate was equipped with new tightly fastened screws.
- 4: Finally, to reduce the amount of vibrations keeping the train parallel to the ground as much as possible, a full ring derived from an insulating mat equipped the ground plate connection surface instead of small tape stripes.

Given the difficulty to analyze the behaviour of a bigger and more articulated train in the small domain available, it was decided to realize a $1/35$ scale model of the Class 66 locomotive only.

Figure 6: Grid dependence analysis. Big markers represent the reference mesh results, other meshes are characterized by $\pm 10\%$ steps on reference cell length. Error bars with a half-length equal to the standard deviation of each sample depicts results convergence.

Figure 7: Details of the wind tunnel and measurement setups. Figure (c) depicts the balance scale and train reference systems (\mathbb{X} - \mathbb{Y} and x - y respectively).

Tests were performed in a range of dynamic pressure that goes from 100 to 230 Pa, corresponding to an estimated speed varying from 12.89 to 19.55 m/s (air temperature is assumed to be $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$, therefore air density is considered equal to $\rho = 1.2 \text{ kg/m}^3$). To be noted that - assuming air viscosity to be equal to $\mu = 1.76 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ - Reynolds number at the maximum achievable speed is about half the limit that ensures flow similarity between model and full-scale flows (2.5×10^5 [4] - Section 5.3.4.5). However, different tests were performed to check Reynolds number independence of the results.

For all the reasons previously explained, measurements were performed for three different cases: with the flow aligned to the longitudinal axis of the train and with a relative angle of $\pm 15^\circ$ between the two directions. To do so, the model was first aligned to the flow direction considering as reference a wool tuft, which was placed on the Pitot tube fold to reduce as much as possible all boundary effects given both from wind tunnel walls and train body. Once defined the 0° position it was possible to carry out all the experiments, acting on flow speed, fixing setup and model orientation.

With reference to Figure 7c, before proceeding with the analysis of the data collected it is necessary to determine the relative angle between the scale reference system \mathbb{X} - \mathbb{Y} and the train one. For the configuration of the system which carries the balance beneath the rotating plate of the wind tunnel, in fact, it stands that the line connecting the axes of the threaded rods supporting the train (i.e. x -axis) is not parallel to the side of the

Figure 8: Angular shift between \mathbb{X} - \mathbb{Y} and x - y reference systems which minimizes transversal force contributes. Signal is divided into smaller time buffers for a better comprehension.

square plate of the scale (i.e. \mathbb{Y} -axis). To determine the angular shift between the two sets of coordinates, measurements for the 0° case were processed varying the rotation angle and selecting the one which minimizes the *root mean square* of the y -component of the force. Figure 8 shows an example of this analysis; the angular shift turned out to be equal to 49.5° .

Once the reference system was determined, measurements were performed for all configurations described in detail in Section 2.2. Only the force data were the subject of our study, analyzing each raw signal as follows:

- data are acquired at a sampling frequency of 125 Hz, each acquisition lasts about 90 seconds.
- The raw signal from the balance (Figure 9a) is transformed from \mathbb{X} - \mathbb{Y}

Figure 9: Example of data processing for a specific run. Wind inclination of 0° , dynamic pressure of 100 Pa

to x - y reference system and processed with a low-pass filter with a cutting frequency of 2 Hz (Figure 9 b).

- Knowing the dynamic pressure P_{dyn} and the frontal area of the train model A_{ref} (0.00739 m^2), force coefficients are computed as $C = F/P_{\text{dyn}} \cdot A_{\text{ref}}$. The analysis focuses mainly on drag coefficient C_x (always referred to the longitudinal axis of the train).
- To neglect spurious data due to unsteady macroscopic oscillations in the system, the analysis involves only a time window in which the signal is assumed to be reliable (Figure 9 c). The average value and the standard deviation of each signal are finally computed.

2.3. Measurement results and comparisons

At this point, an effective way to compare measurement results and simulation data is to plot all C_x / C_l couples on a scatter plot for each of the two wind inclinations tested. In addition to this, each point comes with a rectangular patch of width and height equal to the double of the standard deviation of C_x or C_l sample respectively to visualize data dispersion. Results are presented within Figure 10, measurements setups described in Section 2.2 are identified through differently coloured patches (#1 #2 #3 #4).

With reference to Figure 10a it is possible to draw the following considerations for 0° case:

- overall, measurements related to different

setups and flow speed are comparable.

- C_x values are close to simulations outcome, the slight difference is probably related to an increase of drag due to the interaction of the flow with the tunnel floor and the threaded rods.
- The increase of lift coefficient C_l is likely to be associated to the raise of the train nose, a phenomenon more pronounced when the model is not perfectly parallel to the ground. Considering setup #2 reported in Figure 7c, it is evident that strips of window sealing tape result in a worse alignment than using a full ring or no insulation.

With respect to $\pm 15^\circ$ cases results, shown in Figure 10b, the following aspects could be highlighted:

- despite the symmetry of the model, the results for the two cases appear to be divided into two well separated classes. This is probably due to a different interaction of the air stream with wind tunnel boundaries and train body, as the flow is not perfectly parallel to the longitudinal direction of the testing structure and the head and tail of the model are closer to the walls.
- Results within the same angle class do not depend on the upwind side - i.e. the printed surface or the one shown in Figure 7b sealed with aluminum tape - as both of them were tested with analogous outcomes.
- Considering -15° case, most of C_x values are similar to simulations outcome (but still slightly overestimated). Setups #3 and #4 are the one closer to simulations.

Figure 10: Measurement and simulation results for model validation.

- It is not possible to draw relevant conclusions analyzing C_l results, as they are spread over a wide range of values as a result of a higher influence of model non-parallelism with respect to the floor of the tunnel. Similarly to 0° case, setup #2 resembles to a great dispersion of C_l values for both cases shown in Figure 10 b as a result of a bad alignment of the train model with respect to the floor of the wind tunnel.

3. Full model simulation

Once the CFD model is validated, it is possible to carry out the simulations regarding the full train; the same scale used for the wind tunnel has been maintained in order to have more coherent results with the model validation. Since there is no more need of similarity between measurement setup and simulation domain (considering the characteristic length L , it was considered $16L$ at the rear, $8L$ at the front and $10L$ at the two sides and above the train), a larger mesh (Figure 11) is considered with the aim of reproducing the free air. Conversely, the refinement structure adopted and the wind speed are the same of the wind tunnel model.

Table 1: Number of mesh elements for full model simulations.

	Cells	
	Squared	Blunt
0°	3.87×10^7	3.88×10^7
$3^\circ - 12^\circ$	5.76×10^7	5.77×10^7
$15^\circ - 24^\circ$	7.63×10^7	7.63×10^7

Figure 11: Full model mesh for longitudinal wind (top) and side wind (bottom).

Figure 12: The two types of wagons considered

Simulations for different wind inclinations were realized, keeping the train always parallel to the mesh walls and varying the flow velocity components according to the specific case considered. The main purpose of these simulations is to examine the effects of cross-wind on C_x coefficient, trying to understand how the shape of the wagons (shown in Figure 12) affects this parameter at different wind angles.

In this case, different boundary conditions were imposed with respect to the simulations related to the gallery domain. Considering Figure 14, it is possible to notice that for the 0° case a `movingWall` condition applies to the ground and `symmetryPlane` condition to upper and lateral walls, while in presence of side wind lateral walls are part of inlet and outlet walls.

3.1. Simulations results

First, simulations on the two wagons (Figure 12) in 0° wind condition were carried out, and differences on the C_x coefficient have been immediately noted (Figure 13).

The transition from the locomotive and the first wagon plays a key role in the overall C_x . In Figure 15 it can be highlighted through C_p coefficient [5] how the flow impacts on the wagon surface, in particular the fact that the blunt wagon has a rounded shape on the top, coherent with the one of the locomotive, is very effective in drag reduction.

$$C_p = \frac{p - p_\infty}{\frac{1}{2} \rho U_\infty^2}$$

Subsequently, various simulations with different cross-wind angles were performed, aiming to investigate trend of C_x with respect to wind angle.

Figure 13: C_x over time

(a) Parallel flow condition

(b) Cross-wind condition

Figure 14: Boundary conditions.

Figure 15: Differences in pressure coefficient C_p at the first container for 0° case

Figure 16: C_x behavior for different cross-wind angles. ΔC_x is meant as the relative error among the two squared wagon for a given wind angle.

Considering Figure 16, it is possible to notice a predictable increasing trend in the coefficient as the angle increase for both wagons. It is then interesting to point out that differences in results for a given angle tend to diverge as it increases, as the percentage difference trend shows. In particular, as it can be seen the difference in terms of drag between the two containers tends to increase when α increases, this is because of the different development of the wake (Figure 17). A closer view was done in the section near the first wagon and through some slices (Figure 18) it can be noticed that the slipstream in the blunt one is more adherent and in general more qualitative and less disturbed with respect to the squared one. This behaviour is mainly induced by the presence of a smoother change of surface in first, while in the latter, the presence of a sharp edge leads to a greater flow detachment. To have a general overview of C_x behaviour along the entire train, considering different angles, it's interesting to analyse Figure 19. Looking at the diagrams, a considerable contribution on the overall drag is due to the flow interaction in the zones between locomotive and the first container and between the two wagons, this is always less in the blunt configuration; moreover, also the C_x gradient along the length is higher, highlighting differences in friction contributes.

Figure 17: Wake behavior for 18° case

Figure 18: Wake behaviour in correspondence of first wagon

Figure 19: Cumulative C_x along the train

4. Conclusions

The main purpose of the project was to understand how the drag of the train is affected by the wind angle, with a focus on the different behavior of it when presenting two different shapes. Wind tunnel tests with different setups were performed so to have reliable experimental data to validate the numerical model. Experiments, carried out on a reduced model involving the locomotive only, allowed to verify simulation results and to choose an appropriate mesh element size and refinement strategy. After the numerical setup was approved, a new simulation domain with similar meshing characteristics was generated with the aim to reproduce free air conditions. From simulation results, it was clear that the drag coefficient increases with a quasi-linear trend in both configurations except for a few cases as it can be seen in the ΔC_x behaviour (Figure 16); this is mainly due to the fact that for some specific angles the wake remains more adherent to the train and so the difference of C_p between the two geometries is not so evident. In general, the passage from the squared wagon to another one with a shape more coherent with the shape of the locomotive and that presents a smoother change of surfaces from the side to the top, is very effective in reducing drag and increasing the stability of the train. The CFD analysis highlighted that, depending on the wind angle, the reduction of C_x is in a range between 7%-18% and it is more pronounced as the angle increases.

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